

gradient correction upto second order^{7,8} (i.e. Eqn. 4 without $T_4(\rho)$ term); model-III: TFD model with gradient correction to kinetic energy upto fourth order⁹ (i.e. Eqn. 4). The charge density distribution obtained from the use of the above are used to estimate $J_L(\rho)$ and the results of the study are shown in Table 1. For the first row of atoms,

TABLE 1—CLASSICAL COULOMB ENERGY, $J_L(\rho)$ (ATOMIC UNITS)—LOCAL APPROXIMATION

At. no.	Model			HF*
	I	II	III	
3	4.6	4.0	3.9	4.1
4	8.9	7.8	7.7	7.2
5	14.8	13.3	13.1	11.7
6	22.4	20.4	20.8	17.8
7	31.9	29.8	29.2	26.2
8	43.4	40.2	40.1	36.6
9	56.9	53.0	52.9	50.9
10	72.6	67.9	67.8	66.1

*Ref. 11.

the value of constant B_0 is found to be 0.9058, compared with the values obtained by Bartolotti and Parr¹⁰ being 0.9299. The value obtained by us, for the neutral atoms, is 1.66% (standard percentage error) of the actual or Hartree-Fock values, if the use of Eqn. (3) is made. Furthermore, the results are shown in Table 2 when the addition of the first 'gradient correction' to Eqn. (2) is made, giving the so-called non-local approximation having the formula of the form,

$$J_{NL}(\rho) = BN^{2/3} \int \rho^{4/3} d\tau - CN^{4/3} \int \left(\frac{\nabla \rho}{\rho^{4/3}} \right)^2 d\tau \quad (5)$$

where, B and C are constants having the values 1.8116 and 0.0064 respectively. The justification equation (5) is already discussed¹⁰. By comparing the results of Tables 1 and 2, it is interesting to note that the results improve as one goes from model-I to model-III. In the case of F and Ne atoms model-I seems to be better (Table 2).

TABLE 2—CLASSICAL COULOMB ENERGY, $J_{NL}(\rho)$ (ATOMIC UNITS)—NON-LOCAL APPROXIMATION

At. no.	Model			HF*
	I	II	III	
3	4.2	3.6	3.6	4.1
4	8.0	7.4	7.1	7.2
5	13.4	12.1	12.0	11.7
6	20.8	19.5	18.4	17.8
7	28.9	27.6	26.5	26.2
8	39.4	37.4	36.3	36.6
9	51.6	48.1	48.0	50.9
10	66.8	61.6	61.5	66.1

*Ref. 11.

It appears from the present study that the gradient correction to kinetic energy is quite important for the estimation of $J_L(\rho)$ and $J_{NL}(\rho)$ values. Our next theoretical step is to extend this study to the electron density distribution in an atom-metal interaction.

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Synthesis and Biological Activity of N_1 -Substituted-3-methyl-5-pyrazolones and related Compounds

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PYRAZOLES are found to possess promising antiviral activity¹. Some of the oxopyrazoles exhibit various biological activities². Many pyrazole derivatives possess anti-inflammatory activity³. Irikura⁴ reported that 3,5-dimethyl pyrazolones have anti-diabetic property. We have, therefore, synthesised the title compounds and evaluated their biological activity.

The synthesis involved the condensation of substituted-arylohydrazines with ethyl acetoacetate in dioxane to give ethyl butarate-2-substituted-arylohydrazones (1). **1a-k** on cyclisation in refluxing *o*-dichlorobenzene gave 2-methyl(1-substituted-aryl)-2-pyrazolin-5-ones (**2a-k**), which with an aryl aldehyde in presence of fused sodium acetate and glacial acetic acid yielded the corresponding mono-arylidene derivatives (**3a-x**) (Scheme 1). Compound **3** decolourised bromine water and showed a broad ir peak at 1695 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of ring ketone. The signal due to olefinic proton at δ 5.8 indicates the condensation of the aldehyde with pyrazolone ring at C_4 -position.

Biological activity: All the compounds were tested for their antibacterial activity using cup-plate agar diffusion technique⁵ against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* at 25 and 50 mg ml^{-1} concentration using chloromycetin as a standard (Tables 1 and 2).

Scheme 1

Acetone was used as control in both the cases. The compounds 3h and 3s exhibited strong growth inhibitor activity while 2c, 2d, 2i-k, 3a-c, 3e, 3i, 3o, 3s, 3t, 3n, 3v and 3x were found to be moderately active. All others showed less activity. The presence

of the phenoxy moiety and the halogen atom increases the antibacterial activity. In comparison to pyrazoles the corresponding 4-benzilidene derivatives were found to be more active against gram (+ve) and gram (-ve) bacteria which may be attributed to the reactivity of the ethylenic linkage to certain cellular organisms.

The antifungal activity was tested⁶ against the fungal species *Aspergillus niger* at 1000 ppm concentration. The antifungal data revealed the compounds 2b-d, 2i-k, 3e, 3h, 3i, 3o, 3s, 3t, 3u, 3v and 3x to be moderately active against *Aspergillus niger* while others were found to be less active against the same fungal species. Here, also the N₁-phenoxy substituted arylidene pyrazolones confer better fungicidal activity.

Experimental

Melting points were determined by open capillary method and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer and nmr spectra (TFA) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 instrument using TMS as an internal reference. Homogeneity of the compounds was checked by tlc on silica gel-G plates and the spots were located by exposure to iodine vapour. The compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analysis.

Ethyl butyrate-2-arylhya zones (1): To a solution of the aryl hydrazines (1.95 g, 0.01 mol) in dioxane (20 ml) ethyl acetoacetate (0.65 g, 0.005 mol) was added and the mixture was refluxed gently for 4 h. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the residue poured into ice-cold water. The separated solid was recrystallised from ethanol to furnish 1 (85%), m.p. 110°;

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND BIOLOGICAL SCREENING DATA OF 2

Compd. no.	R	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	N % : Found/ (Calcd.)	Antibacterial activity		Antifungal activity (<i>A. niger</i>)
					<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	
2a	4-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₄ N ₂	193	16.85 (17.00)	+	+	+
2b	4-CH ₃ .O.C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂	250	12.00 (12.06)	+	+	++
2c	2-Cl.C ₆ H ₄ .O.CH ₃	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	185	10.80 (10.50)	++	++	++
2d	2-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	177	11.80 (11.83)	++	+	++
2e	3,5-(NO ₂) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₆ N ₄	125	19.10 (19.17)	+	+	+
2f	2-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .O.CH ₃	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂	198	15.10 (15.16)	+	+	+
2g	O ₂ H ₅ .OH ₂	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂	75	12.80 (12.96)	+	+	+
2h	2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂	270	12.80 (12.84)	+	+	+
2i	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄ .O.CH ₃	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	185	10.82 (10.50)	++	+	++
2j	O ₂ H ₅ -OH=OH	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂	195	12.15 (12.28)	++	++	++
2k	C ₆ H ₅ .O.CH ₃	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂	94	12.00 (12.06)	++	++	++

NOTES

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND BIOLOGICAL SCREENING DATA OF 3

Compd. no.	R	R'	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	N % : Found/ (Calcd.)	Antibacterial activity*		Antifungal activity* <i>A. nigar</i>
						<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	
3a	4-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	4-OH ₂ O	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₅ N ₂	198	14.80 (11.47)	++	+	+
3b	4-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	2-OH	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₅ N ₂	255	11.80 (11.93)	++	+	+
3c	4-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	2-OH	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₅ N ₂	219	11.82 (11.93)	++	+	+
3d	4-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	3-OH	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₅ N ₂	285	11.75 (11.93)	+	+	+
3e	4-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	4-N(OH) ₂	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₂	50	14.70 (14.77)	++	+	++
3f	4-OH ₂ O.C ₆ H ₄	4-OH ₂ O	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₂	115	7.80 (7.97)	+	+	+
3g	4-OH ₂ O.C ₆ H ₄	3-OH	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₂	164	8.10 (8.80)	+	+	+
3h	2-Cl.C ₆ H ₄ .O.OH ₂	3-OH	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₂ Cl	215	7.42 (7.53)	+++	++	++
3i	2-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	4-N(OH) ₂	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	190	11.80 (11.89)	++	+	++
3j	3,5-(NO ₂) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	4-OH	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₇ N ₂	195	14.00 (14.10)	+	+	+
3k	3,5-(NO ₂) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	3-OH	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₇ N ₂	235	14.00 (14.10)	+	+	+
3l	2-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .O.OH ₂	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₅ N ₂	110	11.95 (11.47)	+	++	+
3m	C ₆ H ₅ .OH ₂	4-OH	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₅ N ₂	170	8.65 (8.72)	+	+	+
3n	C ₆ H ₅ .OH ₂	3-OH	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₅ N ₂	225	8.62 (8.72)	+	+	+
3o	C ₆ H ₅ .OH ₂	4-N(OH) ₂	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₂	220	12.00 (12.06)	++	+	++
3p	2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	3-OH	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₂	185	8.50 (8.66)	+	+	+
3q	2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	4-N(OH) ₂	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₂	245	11.80 (12.00)	++	+	+
3r	2-OH.C ₆ H ₄	H	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₅ N ₂	180	8.10 (8.25)	+	+	+
3s	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄ .O.OH ₂	2-OH	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₂ Cl	120	7.45 (7.53)	+++	++	++
3t	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄ .O.OH ₂	4-OH	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₂ Cl	90	7.45 (7.53)	++	++	++
3u	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄ .O.OH ₂	3-OH	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₂ Cl	110	7.40 (7.53)	++	++	++
3v	C ₆ H ₅ .OH=OH	3-OH	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₅ N ₂	190	8.32 (8.40)	++	++	++
3w	C ₆ H ₅ .O.OH ₂	4-OH ₂ O	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₂	105	7.82 (7.97)	+	+	+
3x	4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄ .O.OH ₂	H	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₅ N ₂ Cl	98	7.78 (7.87)	++	++	++

*Zones of inhibition: (+++) = strong growth inhibitor (zone size 15–20 mm), (++) = moderate (9–14 mm), (+) = less (6–8 mm), (–) = no growth inhibitor.

$\nu_{\max}$ 1 720 (C=O ester), 1 600 (C=N) and 1 050 cm⁻¹ (=C–O–C–); δ 1.19 (3H, t, CH₃ ester), 2.15 (3H, s, N=CCH₃), 3.5 (2H, s, CH₂CO), 4.2 (2H, q, CH₂ ester), 6.8–7.5 (4H, m, ArH) and 8.2 (1H, s, CONH exchangeable with D₂O).

*N*₁-*Aroyl/aryloxyacetyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolones* (2a–k): A solution of ethyl butarate-2-aryolhydrazone (3.02 g, 0.01 mol) was refluxed in *o*-dichlorobenzene (20 ml) for ~5 h and the content was left overnight. The resulting solid was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol to yield 2a (74%), m.p. 192°; $\nu_{\max}$ 1 670 (CON), 1 580 (C=N) and 1 050 cm⁻¹ (C–O–C); δ 2.15 (3H, s, N–CCH₃), 2.55 (2H, s, CH₂CO cyclic), 5.5 (1H, s, olefinic), 7–7.5 (4H, m, Ar) and 14.5 (1H, s, OH enolic).

The following forms a general method for the preparation of the compounds 3a–x.

*N*₁-(*p*-Nitrobenzoyl)-3-methyl-4-(*p*-methoxybenzylidene)-2-pyrazolin-5-ones (3f). *General method for preparation of 3*: To *N*₁-(*p*-nitrobenzoyl)-3-methyl-5-pyrazole (0.01 mol) dissolved in glacial acetic acid (5 ml) were added fused sodium acetate (2.0 g) and anisaldehyde (0.01 mol) and the mixture was refluxed for 6 h. It was then cooled and poured into ice-cold water. The resulting solid was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol, (70%), m.p. 123°; $\nu_{\max}$ 1 675 (ring C=O), 1 660 (CO–N), 1 520 (C=N) and 1 020 cm⁻¹ (=C–O–C); δ 2.15 (3H, s, –N–CCH₃), 3.87 (3H, s, OCH₃), 5.8 (1H, s, =CH), (8H, m, ArH).

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Synthesis and Cleavage Reactions of 9-Aryl-4H,8H-pyrano[2,3-f](1,4)benzoxazin-4-one Derivatives

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A good number of 1,4-benzoxazine derivatives are reported to have biological and pharmacological activities¹⁻⁴. The condensed oxazines also possess fluorescent brightening property⁵. Many chromone derivatives act as spasmolytic agents^{6,7}. In continuation of our earlier work on fused 1,4-benzoxazines^{8,9}, we report the synthesis and antimicrobial activity of the title compounds. A few selected pyranobenzoxazine derivatives are cleaved with hydrazine hydrate to form pyrazole derivatives and their biological activity is reported.

The starting materials required for the synthesis of title compounds, 8-amino-7-hydroxy-2-methylchromone (**1a**) and 8-amino-7-hydroxy-2,3-dimethylchromone (**1b**) were prepared by adopting the methods available in literature^{10,11}. Various 9-aryl-4H,8H-pyrano[2,3-f](1,4)benzoxazin-4-ones (**2**) were prepared by the condensation of 2-methyl- and 2,3-dimethyl-7-hydroxy-8-aminochromones (**1a, 1b**) with different phenacyl bromides by refluxing in dry

acetone containing anhydrous potassium carbonate (Scheme 1). They were characterised by their analytical spectral data.

Scheme 1

A strong ir absorption band is found around 1640 cm⁻¹ for the chromone carbonyl function in all the compounds. The stretchings of C=N are observed in the region 1600-1590 cm⁻¹. The pmr spectrum of **2b** displayed two singlets, at δ 3.4 (CH₃) and 5.2 (CH₃). The proton of chromone ring (C-8) absorbed at δ 6.1. The hydrogens of *p*-chlorophenyl nucleus appeared as two doublets at δ 7.45 and 8.41. Another pair of doublets at δ 6.9 and 7.8 are assigned to C-5 and C-6 hydrogens respectively. The molecular ion appeared at *m/z* 305 as the base peak in the mass spectrum of **2e**. Loss of benzonitrile, recorded at *m/z* 103, is one of the prominent cleavages observed in the compound resulting a fragment at *m/z* 202. A peak at *m/z* 252 is assigned for the fragment formed from a cleavage involving retro-Diels-Alder reaction by the elimination of dimethyl acetylene from molecular ion. All the other prominent peaks are also accounted for.

It is interesting to note that the reaction of **2a, b, e, f** with hydrazine hydrate in refluxing alcohol, cleaved the pyranone ring at ethereal oxygen which ultimately afforded 3-aryl-6-(pyrazolo-5-yl)-2H(1,4)-benzoxazin-5-ols (**3a-d**) as shown in Scheme 2. All the products gave deep colouration with neutral ferric chloride, indicating the cleavage of pyrone ring in **2**. The structures of the compounds are assigned on the basis of their analytical and spectral properties.

Scheme 2